
Pilot report

Machine Acts

QUESTION 1

Taking into consideration the Transformational Modules, what concrete steps did the team take to answer the TMs?

Can you please make one case study specific in which you feel the pilot excelled?

(I can't really answer that question, because we didn't take any steps consciously because we didn't know about the TMs. What I could say is this)

We always tried to combine the artistic research with usefulness for future use.

So maybe we can draw a triangle between theoretical methods – artistic methods – adaptivity for the market. How do we do what we do – why do we do what we do – for who/what do we do what we do. That would also mean that we had an entrepreneurial approach.

QUESTION 2

Any challenge or barrier to reporting, in particular in these topics, core to the dynamic clusters:

- interinstitutional collaboration
- interdisciplinary collaboration
- inter-human collaboration

Our pilot was set up as an interdisciplinary collaboration in the first place, so no big barriers to report here. Export for: it takes a effort to leave silo-thinking and silo-working, and be ready to open up yourself for allowing other disciplines interfering with your methods and findings.

Challenges in the in

One challenge was the different hours (FTE) that each institution gave to the researchers. Some officially didn't give any hours at all, some gave 10% or 20% but for a limited time, some were restricted because they couldn't work due to working restriction within their scholarship (and thus were forced to leave the project).

A clear working-hour schedule from the beginning would have helped but we weren't aware of how much work it might be, - so we steered by hand. We also never really had (the need of) a formal agreement between project/uni/FilmEU and researcher.

Having said that, passion for the project and the topic was mainly a reason for the researchers to participate and to do the research.

QUESTION 3

What management /collaboration tool did the Pilot Team use? How did the team use it, for what main purpose, and how did you evaluate it?

In the beginning, our team started to use a combination of Slack and GoogleDrive which facilitated very easy access in a chat-style-informal way of communicating. Both strategic and day-to-day communication were handled in Slack, split up into different work-groups.

After Slack changed their pricing model (10€/month/user), we switched to MS Teams and also transferred the files there. This caused enormous problems as not all had access to Teams, needed to be signed up by external collaborators, and the ongoing log-in problems (caused either by people's ignorance or malfunctioning software) and the file-sharing problems never stopped.

In the case-study with the students (part of the pilot) we tested the open-source collaboration platform cryptpad.fr since it was free and secure. It was easy to use and focusses on collaborative writing and worked quite well for us. But it wasn't widespread and lacked some features like consistent chat, so after the case study was finished, people stopped using it (account-fatigue).

Then we switched back to Teams with a combination of GoogleDrive and Zoom because people continued to have problems with Teams. Moreover MS Teams has huge privacy issues / inbuilt surveillance as has been pointed out by so the collaborators did not want to use it anymore. This software chaos didn't stop us from working, but made clear that there is a desperate need

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.